

LYMC 2024

LISBON YOUNG MATHEMATICIANS CONFERENCE

2024 | 12-13 APRIL

Program and Book of Abstracts

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Preface

Welcome to the Lisbon Young Mathematicians Conference 2024 (LYMC 2024) held at Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa.

LYMC 2024 is the fourth in a series of yearly conferences aiming at bringing together students and young researchers working in Mathematics, Statistics, and Applications, with a view to fostering discussions and collaborations among participants.

The early-career participants of this conference series are encouraged to give talks sharing their work. You will find their abstracts in this booklet, which also includes the abstracts of the talks of the plenary speakers. The latter talks, given by leading mathematicians, are intended to further inspire and stimulate the flow of ideas among those attending the conference.

On behalf of the LYMC 2024 organization, we would like to express our gratitude to the institutions that contributed to make this conference possible: Instituto Superior Técnico, Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, Centro de Análise Matemática, Geometria e Sistemas Dinâmicos (CAMGSD), Centro de Matemática Aplicada à Previsão e à Decisão Económica (CEMAPRE), Centro de Matemática Computacional e Estocástica (CEMAT), and Grupo de Física Matemática (GFM).

We wish you an inspiring experience!

Lisbon, April 2024

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Pedro R. S. Antunes,
Catarina P. Loureiro,
Lina Oliveira,
Diogo Pinheiro,
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Venue

The Conference LYMC 2024 takes place at the Civil Engineering building (Pavilhão de Civil) at the Alameda Campus of Instituto Superior Técnico (IST).

Alameda Campus of IST can be reached by subway (Metro). Take the red or yellow lines and exit at Saldanha towards Av. Duque de Ávila and enter IST by climbing the stairs from R. Alves Redol, or exit at Alameda and walk uphill towards the IST main entrance.

The location of the Civil Engineering building is illustrated in the following map of the IST Campus.

Wi-Fi Connection

The IST Campus has access to the eduroam network. Participants who do not have access to eduroam can have web connection by following these steps:

1. Browse available wireless networks and select SSID 'tecnico-guest';
2. Set IP to automatic (DHCP). This is usually the default setting, so you may probably skip this step;
3. Open your browser and try to access any external website. You will be automatically redirected to the page <https://wifi.ist.utl.pt/index.php>. Follow the link 'Web based login' at the top of the page concerning short-time, conference and meetings accounts. Enter the following user-name/password when requested.

Login credentials:

Username: LYMC2024

Password: TjBwM9

4. After step 3 you may freely browse and access the Internet. You may need to repeat the above steps if you close your browser or if the connection times out.

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Program Overview

Friday, 12th April

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09:30	Opening Session - Room VA4	
10:00	Plenary Talk I - Room VA4	
	Real Toric Lagrangians	Ana Cannas
10:30	Coffee Break	
11:00	Parallel Sessions I	
	Room VA1	Room VA2
11:00	Weakly amenable étale measured groupoids	On the index of some graph matrices
11:15	Relative Gromov–Witten and maximal contact conics	The commuting graph of a Rees matrix semi-group over a group
11:30	Taking endomorphism monoids inductively	Extensions of node-depot assignment formulations for the hamiltonian p -median problem
11:45	From plactic monoids to hypoplactic monoids	A fractional order SIR model describing hesitancy to the COVID-19 vaccination campaign in Portugal
12:00	Plactic-like monoids arising from meets and joins of stalactic and taiga congruences	Integro-differential SIR model with distributed contacts
12:15	Herbrandized modified realizability	Mean distance on metric graphs
12:30	Lunch Time	
14:00	Plenary Talk II - Room VA4	
	Mathematical models for mosquito and pest population control	
	Luís Almeida	
14:35	Parallel Sessions II	
	Room VA1	Room VA2
14:35	Regularity of Lyapunov exponents for random cocycles	A robust covariance matrix estimator for interval-valued data
14:50	From particle systems to PDEs	Selection of network biomarkers in gliomas via robust sparse network discovery and classification
15:05	Approximation of non-local coagulation-fragmentation equations by quasilinear PDEs	Using satellite Earth observations for assessing carbon sequestration
15:20	Stochastic differential equations harvesting models	A new algorithm for inference in Hidden Markov models with lower span complexity
15:35	Boundary control for problems with mixed boundary conditions	Unravelling the mathematical tapestry – charting the statistical terrain: navigating complexity in social science statistical studies, exploring the intricacies of social science research through mathematical lens
15:50		Financial literacy as part of statistical literacy
16:05	Coffee Break	

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16:35	Parallel Sessions III	
	Room VA1	Room VA2
16:35	Control problems with DDN-NS equations	Fantastic normed spaces and where to find them
16:50	An iterated local search algorithm for the traveling purchaser problem	A Brown–Halmos theorem for generalised Toeplitz operators
17:05	Optimal control of a class of stochastic 3rd grade fluids equations	Discrete Wiener–Hopf operators on Orlicz sequence spaces
17:20	Time-dependent strategy for enhanced blood flow modeling with boundary control	Fredholm criteria for the algebra generated by Wiener–Hopf operators with continuous symbols on Orlicz spaces
17:35	The MFS-SVD method for the Laplace equation in three dimensions	Self-improving boundedness of the Hardy–Littlewood maximal operator over spaces of homogeneous type
17:50	Improving the conditioning of the method of fundamental solutions for the Helmholtz equation on domains in polar or elliptic coordinates	Polynomial collocation method for a class of singular fractional differential equations

Saturday, 13th April

09:00	Registration - Pavilhão de Civil, Floor –1	
09:30	Plenary Talk III - Room VA4 Pendulum clocks, spontaneous synchronization (and detecting communities in networks) Afonso Bandeira	
10:05	Parallel Sessions IV	
	Room VA1	Room VA2
10:05	The marginalized LASSO estimator in difference-based partially linear models	Free-falling motion of an elastic rigid rod towards a Schwarzschild black hole
10:20	Machine learning algorithms to predict the solar and wind energies supply profiles	Topics in Laplace transforms
10:35	A classification method based on a cloud of spheres	Resurgence of multicritical strings
10:50	Visualizing interval Fisher’s Discriminant Analysis results	Pinching topological recursion
11:05	Deep Learning for parameter estimation in reaction-diffusion PDEs for battery modeling	A physical primality test
11:20	Least energy solutions for coupled Schrödinger equations with Neumann boundary conditions	A numerical scheme for optimization of Dirac eigenvalues
11:35	Coffee Break	
12:05	NMATH: Mathematics Student Group at IST - Room VA4	
12:20	Plenary Talk IV - Room VA4 On the design of discrete diffusion filters Sílvia Barbeiro	
12:50	Closing Session - Room VA4	

Program

Friday, 12th April

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9:30 **Opening Session** - Room VA4

10:00 **Plenary Talk I** - Room VA4
Real Toric Lagrangians
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Chair: Fernanda Cipriano

10:30 **Coffee Break**

11:00 **Parallel Sessions I**

Room VA1

Chair: Fernanda Cipriano

Room VA2

Chair: Carlota Gonçalves

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11:15 **Relative Gromov–Witten and maximal contact conics**, Giosuè Muratore, p. 9

The commuting graph of a Rees matrix semigroup over a group, Tânia Paulista, p. 16

11:30 **Taking endomorphism monoids inductively**, Ambroise Grau, Victoria Gould, Marianne Johnson, p. 10

Extensions of node-depot assignment formulations for the hamiltonian p -median problem, Francisco Canas, Luís Gouveia, p. 17

11:45 **From plactic monoids to hypoplactic monoids**, Ricardo Guilherme, p. 11

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12:15 **Herbrandized modified realizability**, Paulo Firmino, Gilda Ferreira, p. 13

Mean distance on metric graphs, Luís Baptista, p. 20

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14:50	From particle systems to PDEs , <u>Beatriz Salvador</u> , p. 23	Selection of network biomarkers in gliomas via robust sparse network discovery and classification , <u>João F. Carrilho</u> , Roberta Coletti, Marta B. Lopes, p. 29
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15:20	Stochastic differential equations harvesting models , <u>Miguel Reis</u> , Nuno M. Brites, p. 25	A new algorithm for inference in Hidden Markov models with lower span complexity , <u>Diogo Pereira</u> , Cláudia Nunes, Rui Rodrigues, p. 31
15:35	Boundary control for problems with mixed boundary conditions , <u>Dinis Rocha</u> , p. 26	Unravelling the mathematical tapestry – charting the statistical terrain: navigating complexity in social science statistical studies, exploring the intricacies of social science research through mathematical lens , <u>João Miguel Alves Ferreira</u> , <u>Sergii Tukaiev</u> , p. 32
15:50		Financial literacy as part of statistical literacy , <u>Rosina Ramos</u> , p. 33
16:05	Coffee Break	

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17:05 Optimal control of a class of stochastic 3rd grade fluids equations , <u>Raya Nouira</u> , Fernanda Cipriano, p. 37	Discrete Wiener–Hopf operators on Orlicz sequence spaces , <u>Sandra Thampi</u> , p. 44
17:20 Time-dependent strategy for enhanced blood flow modeling with boundary control , <u>Muhammad Adnan Anwar</u> , Jorge Tiago, p. 38	Fredholm criteria for the algebra generated by Wiener–Hopf operators with continuous symbols on Orlicz spaces , <u>Márcio Valente</u> , p. 45
17:35 The MFS-SVD method for the Laplace equation in three dimensions , <u>Vinicius Santos</u> , Pedro R.S. Antunes, Pedro Serranho, p. 39	Self-improving boundedness of the Hardy–Littlewood maximal operator over spaces of homogeneous type , <u>Alina Shalukhina</u> , p. 46
17:50 Improving the conditioning of the method of fundamental solutions for the Helmholtz equation on domains in polar or elliptic coordinates , <u>Hernani Calunga</u> , Pedro R.S. Antunes, Pedro Serranho, p. 40	Polynomial collocation method for a class of singular fractional differential equations , <u>Ghulam Abbas Khan</u> , K. Lätt, M. Rebelo, p. 47

Saturday, 13th April

9:00 **Registration** - Pavilhão de Civil, Floor -1

9:30 **Plenary Talk III** - Room VA4
Pendulum clocks, spontaneous synchronization (and detecting communities in networks)
 Afonso Bandeira, p. 4

Chair: M. Rosário Oliveira

10:05 **Parallel Sessions IV**

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10:20	Machine learning algorithms to predict the solar and wind energies supply profiles , <u>Mafalda Sá Ferreira</u> , Regina Bispo, p. 50	Topics in Laplace transforms , <u>João Fontinha</u> , p. 57
10:35	A classification method based on a cloud of spheres , <u>Tiago Dias</u> , Paula Amaral, p. 51	Resurgence of multicritical strings , <u>Jasker Kager</u> , p. 58
10:50	Visualizing interval Fisher's Discriminant Analysis results , <u>Diogo Pinheiro</u> , M. Rosário Oliveira, Lina Oliveira, p. 52	Pinching topological recursion , <u>João Rodrigues</u> , Luís Gouveia, p. 59
11:05	Deep Learning for parameter estimation in reaction-diffusion PDEs for battery modeling , <u>Maria Grazia Quarta</u> , Ivonne Sgura, Benedetto Bozzini, Luca Mainetti, p. 53	A physical primality test , <u>Francisco Albuquerque-Picado</u> , p. 60
11:20	Least energy solutions for coupled Schrödinger equations with Neumann boundary conditions , <u>Simone Mauro</u> , Annamaria Canino, Delia Schiera, Hugo Tavares, p. 54	A numerical scheme for optimization of Dirac eigenvalues , Pedro R. S. Antunes, <u>Francisco Bento</u> , David Krejčířík, p. 61

11:35 **Coffee Break**

12:05 **NMATH - Mathematics Student Group at IST - Room VA4**

12:20 **Plenary Talk IV - Room VA4**
On the design of discrete diffusion filters
Sílvia Barbeiro, p. 5

Chair: Pedro Serranho

12:50 **Closing Session - Room VA4**

Plenary Talks

Plenary Talk I, Friday, 12th April, 10:00-10:30, VA4

Real Toric Lagrangians

Ana Cannas^{1,*}

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Abstract

Lagrangian submanifolds lie at the core of Symplectic Geometry – the geometry of manifolds equipped with a closed nondegenerate 2-form, which include all phase spaces from Physics. Toric symplectic manifolds form a most symmetric class of symplectic manifolds. After a brief review of these spaces, this talk will explain a classification of lagrangian submanifolds best fitting the symmetry and generalizing real projective spaces inside complex projective spaces. This is joint work with Yael Karshon.

Mathematical models for mosquito and pest population control

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Abstract

Due to urbanization, global travel and exchanges and climate change, the burden of malaria, dengue, Zika and other mosquito-borne diseases is among the most important public health problems worldwide. Most dengue control programmes today rely on conventional mosquito abatement methods that are resource intensive and often unsustainable since the insecticides pollute the environment and severely impact biodiversity. Moreover, mosquito vectors rapidly develop insecticide resistance which reduces control effectiveness. The situation is compounded by the rapid and global expansion of the invasive tiger mosquito (which has rapidly progressed in Europe, including Portugal, in recent years).

Alternative methods for disease vector population control are thus an essential part of epidemic prevention worldwide, in particular for mosquito-borne diseases. Among these novel control methods, the sterile incompatible and insect techniques (SIT, IIT) and replacement strategies have gained traction in the scientific community.

In this talk we will see some mathematical models for disease vector population control and how mathematics can be used to conceive robust control strategies or optimize the intervention cost while minimizing its environmental impact. Similar models can also be used in agro-ecology for pest control.

Plenary Talk III, Saturday, 13th April, 09:30-10:00, VA4

Pendulum clocks, spontaneous synchronization (and detecting communities in networks)

Afonso S. Bandeira^{1,*}

¹ ETH Zürich,

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Abstract

In the 1600s, Christiaan Huygens realized that two pendulum clocks (an invention of his!) placed in the same wooden table eventually fall into synchrony. Since then, synchronization of coupled oscillators has been an important subject of study in classical mechanics and nonlinear dynamics. In this talk we will discuss spontaneous synchronization (in the, so called, Kuramoto model) and, if time permits, relate it to the performance of certain algorithms in the problem of detecting communities in graphs (a central problem in network science).

On the design of discrete diffusion filters

Sílvia Barbeiro^{1,*}

¹ CMUC, Department of Mathematics, University of Coimbra

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Abstract

Image restoration is one of the major concerns in image processing with many interesting applications. In the last decades there has been intensive research around the topic and hence new approaches are constantly emerging. Partial differential equation (PDE) based models, namely of non-linear diffusion type, are well-known and widely used for image noise removal. In this talk we will start with a concise introduction about reaction diffusion models for image restoration. Then we will explore fully-discrete filters which reveal similar features as their continuous counterparts as scale-space invariances as well as the existence of Lyapunov functions. Finally, we will discuss a flexible learning framework in order to optimize the parameters of the model improving the quality of the denoising process.

Contributed Talks

Session I

Friday, 12th April, 11:00-12:30, VA1

Weakly amenable étale measured groupoids

Tomás Pacheco^{1,*}

¹ Instituto Superior Técnico, *tomas.pacheco@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Abstract

The main goal is to generalize the concept of *weak amenability* to the case of groupoids, more specifically, étale measured groupoids. This is motivated by the need to give a sufficient condition for a groupoid to be *localizable* in the sense of [4].

First I give an overview of the representation theory of measured groupoids (G_2, μ) . After, I define the Fourier-Stieltjes and Fourier algebras $B(G_2)$, $A(G_2)$ of a measured groupoid introduced by J. Renault in [3]. It is given a duality theory of $B(G_2)$ and $A(G_2)$, concretely, it is proven that there is an isometry

$$B(G_2) \rightarrow \left(L^\infty(\mathcal{G}^{(0)}) \otimes_{h\mathcal{G}^{(0)}} C_\mu^*(G_2) \otimes_{h\mathcal{G}^{(0)}} L^\infty(\mathcal{G}^{(0)}) \right)^*$$

moreover, it is also proven in [3, Theorem 2.3] there is a completely isometric $*$ -isomorphism $VN(G_2)_* \cong L^\infty(\mathcal{G}^{(0)}) \otimes_{h\mathcal{G}^{(0)}} A(G_2) \otimes_{h\mathcal{G}^{(0)}} L^\infty(\mathcal{G}^{(0)})$. This will allow us to relate the multiplier algebras $MA(G_2)$ and $M_0A(G_2)$ with operators on $C_\lambda^*(G_2)$, $VN(G_2)$.

Like it was done for the case of amenable groupoids, to motivate our definition we use the example of the transformation groupoid, studying weak amenability of dynamical systems and their multipliers using [2].

We define **weak amenability** of an étale measured groupoid: there exists a net of completely bounded multipliers with compact support $(\varphi_i) \in M_0A(G_2)$ such that $\varphi_i \rightarrow 1$ uniformly on compact sets. We prove the above condition is equivalent to $C_\lambda^*(G_2)$ having the CBAP, meaning there exists a net (M_i) converging strongly to the identity operator on $C_\lambda^*(G_2)$. By [3] if $\varphi \in M_0A(G_2)$, then it induces an operator $M_\varphi : VN(G_2) \rightarrow VN(G_2)$ from which we can obtain $\overline{M}_\varphi : C_\lambda^*(G_2) \rightarrow C_\lambda^*(G_2)$. If (φ_i) is a net that verifies the conditions of weak amenability then the operators $(\overline{M}_{\varphi_i})$ verify that $C_\lambda^*(G_2)$ has the CBAP. Conversely, in [1] is defined a canonical conditional expectation $E : C_\lambda^*(G_2) \rightarrow C_0(\mathcal{G}^{(0)})$ and a canonical trace associated with μ , $\tau_\mu : C_\lambda^*(G_2) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$. Through them, if we have a net (M_i) of completely bounded finite rank operators on $C_\lambda^*(G_2)$, we will be able to construct a net (φ_{M_i}) that proves G_2 is weakly amenable.

References

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- [3] Renault, J. “The Fourier algebra of a Measured Groupoid and its Multipliers,” Journal of Functional Analysis, **145**, No. 2, 455–490 (1997).
- [4] Resende, P. “Quantales and Fell Bundles,” Advances in Mathematics, **325**, 312–374 (2018).

Relative Gromov–Witten and maximal contact conics

Giosuè Muratore^{1,*},

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Abstract

Let Y be a complex general smooth plane curve of degree $d \geq 3$. According to the classical Bézout’s Theorem, a rational curve of degree n meets Y at dn points. If we require that the contact order at some point is $3n$ (the maximal possible), we expect that the number of such rational curves is finite. For example, if $n = 1$ these curves are the inflectional lines. A classical result says that the number of such lines is described by the polynomial

$$3d(d - 2).$$

When $n = 2$, maximal tangent curves are called sextactic conics, and the relevant intersection point is called sextactic point. Cayley [1] proved that the number of these conics is given by the polynomial

$$n_d = 3d(4d - 9).$$

In this talk, we provide an original proof of Cayley’s result that uses relative Gromov–Witten invariants, introduced in [2]. These invariants are virtual counts of stable maps tangent to the curve Y . In particular, we prove that n_d can be obtained by intersection theory involving some virtual fundamental classes. One of these classes is the class of the double covers of inflectional lines of Y , which does not have the expected dimension.

Our findings are corroborated by the multiple cover contribution formula of Gross, Pandharipande, and Siebert [3]. Finally, we show how our work could be extended by increasing the degree of the tangent curve n or the dimension of the hypersurface Y . These counts are currently known only in very specific cases.

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Taking endomorphism monoids inductively

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Abstract

The full transformation monoid \mathcal{T}_n consisting of all maps from the set $\{1, \dots, n\}$ into itself, is possibly the most important example of a finite monoid and the first example of a monoid of endomorphisms. The description of the elements in the endomorphism monoid $\text{End}(\mathcal{T}_n)$ of \mathcal{T}_n was given by Schein and Teclezghi [1]. Surprisingly, the algebraic structure of this monoid has not been further investigated. In this talk, we will describe some key properties of $\text{End}(\mathcal{T}_n)$ in comparison with those of \mathcal{T}_n and discuss why the process of taking endomorphism monoids inductively does not come for free and must be dealt with carefully.

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From plactic monoids to hypoplactic monoids

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Abstract

The plactic monoid, introduced by Lascoux and Schützenberger [6], can be obtained by identifying words in the same position of isomorphic connected components of a Kashiwara crystal of Cartan type A . Based on crystals and their tensor product, this method allows the generalization of the plactic monoid, because the construction can be applied to crystals of another type (e.g. [4; 5]).

In joint work with Cain and Malheiro [1], quasi-crystals and their quasi-tensor product were introduced from which the hypoplactic monoid, obtained by Krob and Thibon [3], arises by identifying words in the same position of isomorphic connected components of a quasi-crystal of type A . This construction allows the generalization of the hypoplactic monoid.

In this talk, following the work in [2], we present a unified approach to plactic and hypoplactic monoids through quasi-crystals. We show how to obtain a quasi-crystal monoid for the quasi-tensor product from a quasi-crystal monoid for the tensor product. We also establish a sufficient condition for a hypoplactic monoid to be a quotient of the plactic monoid associated to the same seminormal quasi-crystal.

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Plactic-like monoids arising from meets and joins of stalactic and taiga congruences

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Abstract

The (left) stalactic monoid was introduced by Hivert, Novelli and Thibon [1] as the analogue of the plactic monoid for Hopf algebras of word symmetric functions, whose associated combinatorial objects are stalactic tableaux. The (right) taiga monoid was defined by Priez [2] as the quotient of the free monoid over an ordered alphabet by the join of the sylvester [3] and (right) stalactic congruences. Its associated combinatorial objects are binary search trees with multiplicities, for which a Robinson–Schensted-like correspondence and ‘hook-length’-like formula are given. The equational theories of these monoids have been studied in [4; 5], where they were shown to generate the same variety.

We study the four plactic-like monoids that arise by taking the meets and joins of stalactic and taiga congruences, following the construction of the Baxter monoid given by Giraudo [6]. We obtain the combinatorial objects associated with the meet monoids, establishing Robinson–Schensted-like correspondences and giving extraction and iterative insertion algorithms for these objects. We then obtain results on the sizes of classes of words equal in plactic-like monoids, show that some of these monoids are syntactic, and characterise their equational theories.

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Herbrandized modified realizability

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Abstract

In this talk, we present a new notion of realizability, the *herbrandized modified realizability* [2]. Realizability notions in mathematical logic can be traced back to the work of Stephen Kleene in the 1940s, which laid the ground for more sophisticated notions such as Kreisel's modified realizability and various modern approaches. In this context, our work aligns with the lineage of realizability strategies that emphasize the accumulation rather than the propagation of precise witnesses. The herbrandized modified realizability, a novel form of (cumulative) realizability, presented within the framework of semi-intuitionistic logic, is based on a recently developed *star combinatory calculus* [1] which enables the gathering of witnesses into nonempty finite sets. We also show that the previous analysis can be extended from logic to (Heyting) arithmetic.

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Session II

Friday, 12th April, 11:00-12:30, VA2

On the index of some graph matrices

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Abstract

A fundamental problem in graph matrices is to characterize the invertibility of such matrices and to provide a formula for the inverse. This problem is naturally generalised to pseudo-invertibility.

We will address the problem of determining the Drazin inverse of matrices associated to certain classes of digraphs, primarily using the characterisation of the Drazin index by the minimal polynomial of the graph matrix.

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The commuting graph of a Rees matrix semigroup over a group

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Abstract

The commuting graph of a finite non-commutative semigroup S is a simple graph whose vertices are the non-central elements of S , and where two distinct vertices $x, y \in S$ are adjacent if and only if $xy = yx$.

We characterize the commuting graph of a Rees matrix semigroup over a group, and determine some of the properties of this graph – connectedness, diameter, clique number, chromatic number, girth and knit degree.

The interest of studying Rees matrix semigroups over groups comes from the fact that they allow us to characterize completely simple semigroups: a semigroup is completely simple if and only if it is isomorphic to a Rees matrix semigroup over a group. This way, studying the commuting graph of a Rees matrix semigroup over a group will provide us with information regarding the properties of commuting graphs of completely simple semigroups.

Extensions of node-depot assignment formulations for the hamiltonian p -median problem

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Abstract

Given a weighted complete undirected graph $G = (V, E)$ with weights on the edges and a positive integer p , the symmetric Hamiltonian p -Median Problem (HpMP) on G is to find a minimum weight set of p elementary cycles partitioning the vertices of G . We focus on a variant of the HpMP (the HpMP_≥) where solutions with strictly more than p cycles are also feasible.

We begin by discussing known node-depot assignment (NDA) formulations. NDA models are characterized by the inclusion of NDA variables h_i^d , which are 1 if and only if node d acts as the depot of the cycle node i is in, in addition to edge variables u_{ij} , which are 1 if and only if edge $\{i, j\}$ is in some cycle.

We extend these formulations with edge-depot assignment variables z_{ij}^d , which are 1 if and only if node d acts as the depot of the cycle edge $\{i, j\}$ is in. In this talk, we:

- i*) propose new formulations which use these variables;
- ii*) relate these models with formulations including only the u_{ij} and h_i^d variables;
- iii*) present new inequalities in the space of the u_{ij} and h_i^d variables that are derived from the new models using edge-based variables;
- iv*) present computational results obtained with the new models.

Preliminary computational results show that the new models produce very strong LP relaxation bounds and, when used in combination with a modern ILP solver, allow for the resolution of instances with over one-hundred nodes.

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A fractional order SIR model describing hesitancy to the COVID-19 vaccination campaign in Portugal

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Abstract

In this study, we develop a fractional order susceptible-infected-recovered model incorporating a vaccination process with associated Mittag-Leffler distributed times until vaccination. The classical ordinary differential equations model can be obtained when the fractional order is 1. We study the qualitative properties of the model, namely its equilibria and associated stability. Using statistical model selection criteria we show that the Mittag-leffer assumption provides a better fit compared to the classic exponential distribution, i.e. the fractional order $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ for times until vaccination observed during the COVID-19 vaccination campaign in Portugal 2021. Leveraging the model and the statistical results, we perform numerical simulations for the evolution of possible epidemics where the results of the classic model ($\alpha = 1$) are compared to the fractional model, ($\alpha \in (0, 1)$). Finally, we provide an epidemiological interpretation of the fractional order, tying it to vaccination hesitancy.

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Integro-differential SIR model with distributed contacts

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Abstract

Classical epidemic models are generally described by compartmental models that do not include spatial heterogeneity. Based on the literature review on spatial heterogeneous models, there are mainly two ways to include spatial dependence designated by Eulerian and Lagrangian approaches [3], or as Distributed-Infectives (DI) and Distributed-Contacts (DC), respectively [4]. In the Eulerian approach, we follow the movement of individuals, assuming that the contacts are local whereas, in the Lagrangian approach, we follow the individuals' contacts and not their movement, maintaining the population constant throughout space.

We will focus on the Lagrangian approach. We consider an integro-differential SIR model with vital dynamics. We determine the basic reproduction number, R_0 , based on Diekmann's next-generation operator [1], and we study the stability of the disease-free equilibrium depending on R_0 [1; 2]. Finally, we will show numerical results for the endemic equilibrium.

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Mean distance on metric graphs

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Abstract

Although (discrete) graphs are well understood and very useful in many different contexts, when the context demands a distance and not just a relation (or weighted relations), the preferred object is a metric graph, where each edge can be identified with an interval.

Since the 1990s, with the studies of Bojan Mohar [3], we know about a connection in (discrete) graphs linking the mean distance between vertices (which is obtained by summing the distances between every pair of vertices and dividing by the total number of vertex pairs) and the eigenvalues of the (discrete) Laplacian, particularly its smallest nontrivial eigenvalue, the so-called spectral gap.

In this talk, we will first introduce the concept of mean distance on metric graphs. Subsequently, we will explore its connection to the well-established spectral gap [2], represented by the first non-zero eigenvalue of the Laplacian.

This is based on joint work with James Kennedy and Delio Mugnolo [1].

References

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Session III

Friday, 12th April, 14:35-16:05, VA1

Regularity of Lyapunov exponents for random cocycles

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Abstract

The notion of Lyapunov exponent is a central concept in ergodic theory and in the theory of smooth dynamical systems, which measures the sensitivity of the dynamical system with respect to the initial conditions. We study the regularity of the Lyapunov exponents in the context of linear cocycles (see [1]), which is a class of dynamical systems over fiber bundles that preserves the linear bundle structure and induces a measure preserving dynamical system on the base. The dependency of the Lyapunov exponents as a function of the law that determines the system can be extremely irregular. We present some results with respect to some specific class of dynamics regarding the regularity of the Lyapunov exponents, namely that in the non-invertible two-dimensional case the Lyapunov exponent is either analytic or discontinuous (P. Duarte, M. Durães, T. G. and S. Klein) and that under some generic hypothesis, the Lyapunov exponent for non-compact random cocycles is Hölder continuous (P. Duarte and T. G.). We also present some statistical properties of these dynamical systems, such as large deviation type estimates.

References

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From particle systems to PDEs

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Abstract

We will start by introducing a specific interacting particle system for which we derive its hydrodynamic limit. The model we will analyse is an exclusion process defined in $\{1/N, \dots, (N-1)/N\}$ with weak interaction with boundary reservoirs that allow the creation and annihilation of particles on a neighborhood of radius l of the boundary points 0 and 1. We will show that the hydrodynamic equation associated to the process is the heat equation with non-linear Robin boundary conditions, for which the problem of uniqueness of solution will be discussed.

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Approximation of non-local coagulation-fragmentation equations by quasilinear PDEs

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Abstract

Coagulation-fragmentation equations are under a suitable change of variables non-local conservation laws (integro-differential). Let's restrict our considerations to coagulation processes. They are intended to describe aggregation phenomena ruled by binary collisions of clusters in a homogeneously diluted system [1; 3]. In some special cases unexpected oscillation behaviours were numerically observed [2]. We use approximations of the non-local coagulation equation by quasilinear dissipative-dispersive equations to study those behaviours. We look for their travelling wave solutions and numerical simulations.

References

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Stochastic differential equations harvesting models

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Abstract

Harvesting is a primary and fundamental activity impacting on human society as a food supplier and on the environment as a resource consumer. An equilibrium, required to keep environments healthy and the activity attractive, is attainable through the application of a sustainable strategy, driven by effort. In fisheries, effort is the action plan measured by the number of vessels, workers, hours, among other factors, which impose low flexibility to organisations. Effort is obtained through the solution of a non-linear Partial Differential Equation, arising from the optimisation process. Optimal variable effort yields the highest profits and is crucial to evaluate the feasibility of other strategies. However, highly volatile effort policies are inapplicable due to logistic and social issues. A penalised effort strategy was applied to study effort's new behaviour and profit. Impact on profit depends on the strength of the penalisation parameter—the higher (lower) this value, the higher (lower) the impact on effort and the lower (higher) the profit. Penalised effort does not oscillate as sharply as the non-penalised, but it is constantly adjusted. Thus, penalised effort removes social issues imposed by low or null effort periods, leaving the logistic subject as the source of uncertainty to its implementation.

Boundary control for problems with mixed boundary conditions

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Abstract

In the field of data assimilation, a problem of interest is the numerical approximation of the state of a physical system, given some observation and a mathematical model describing it. The mathematical model is very often a Partial Differential Equation (PDE), and the state is determined by a boundary condition, for example. One approach to the data assimilation problem is to pose it as an optimal control problem, where the boundary condition serves as the control and we seek to minimize the distance (usually in L^2) between the corresponding state and the observation [1]. Well-posedness of the problem requires a penalisation through some norm of the control, and computational considerations make the choice of the L^2 norm appealing. However, this comes with a cost, since now we should look for the boundary condition in L^2 , and thus must consider a weaker formulation of the governing PDE. A relevant application is that of blood flow in an artery. There, the blood velocity field is the state and the inlet velocity profile in part of the artificial boundary is the the control. In fact, it is also practical to consider another type of boundary condition at some other part of the boundary assumed to be the outlet. In this work, we consider a two dimensional toy model, in which we allow the domain to be non-convex, so that it might represent an arterial bifurcation, for example. We also consider the numerical analysis of its approximation with the Finite Element Method (FEM). To this end, we build on the work in [3], where well-posedness, regularity and optimal error estimates for the FEM for the convex Dirichlet case, to the non-convex, mixed boundary one. The main difficulty in doing so is the loss of regularity of the solutions, which we overcome by imposing suitable constraints on the domain and employing the well-known regularity results in [4].

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Session IV

Friday, 12th April, 14:35-16:05, VA2

A robust covariance matrix estimator for interval-valued data

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Abstract

Interval-valued data is one of the most common symbolic data types, which enables the preservation of inherent variability in the data while simultaneously reducing the dataset size. The symbolic mean and symbolic covariance matrix can be obtained using the barycentre approach based on the Mallows' distance [1]. However, the accuracy and reliability of classical fitted models can be significantly affected by anomalous data points present in real-life datasets, resulting in the need for robust models. In this work, we obtain a robust symbolic covariance matrix using the Minimum Covariance Determinant (MCD) estimator [2] for interval-valued data. We start by formulating the optimization problem [3]. The Majorization-Minorization algorithm [4] is then employed to derive the MCD algorithm for interval-valued data. As a product of this algorithm, we obtain a robust distance that can be used to detect anomalous observations. The applicability of the interval-valued MCD estimator is illustrated through some examples. The robust symbolic mean and covariance matrix are obtained, while the anomalous observations are reliably detected.

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References

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Selection of network biomarkers in gliomas via robust sparse network discovery and classification

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Abstract

Gliomas are highly heterogenous brain tumors characterized by generally poor prognoses, being fundamental to get increasingly deeper understanding of this disease's biological mechanisms. Identifying changes in individual molecular entities and their roles within broader molecular networks is essential for understanding glioma heterogeneity. This can be achieved through the application of statistical and network inference methods on omics datasets, marked by their high dimensionality.

The proposed methodology consists on a feature selection approach to infer glioma transcriptomic network biomarkers and classify patients into distinct glioma types. Using data from The Cancer Genome Atlas, the joint graphical lasso (JGL) algorithm [1] is first applied to identify unique features associated with the three main glioma types, i.e., astrocytoma, oligodendroglioma, and glioblastoma, along with shared features among those. It is followed by the application of robust sparse multinomial regression techniques [2] to estimate the suitability of considering prior network-based information in glioma type separation.

The sparse networks obtained through the application of JGL to glioma transcriptomic data highlight type-exclusive and shared gene connections across glioma types. Classification considering both the full set of features and those within identified subnetworks achieved high performance, with the subnetworks outperforming the full set of features in terms of classification accuracy. Furthermore, sparse networks facilitate the identification of relevant diagnostic genes as well as the estimation of underlying relations that aid in disease understanding. Future natural steps might involve further biological validation of identified molecular features as potential biomarkers.

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Using satellite Earth observations for assessing carbon sequestration

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Abstract

Forests have played an important role in mitigating climate change, [1]. The quantification and monitoring of the amount of carbon in forests has been crucial tool for understanding climate change, to define the global policies and help with the emerging market in carbon credits. Biomass quantification can be used to quantify the amount of carbon, using the following relationship: $\text{Carbon} = \text{AGB} \times 0.5$, where AGB is the above ground biomass. The estimation of the AGB can be done using direct or indirect methods. The direct methods involve the destruction of the trees while the indirect methods don't. However, the indirect methods involve data collection from forest inventories which are expensive and time-consuming processes. An alternative made possible with the development of technology, is remote sensing estimation, where the remote data collected through satellites can be used in conjunction with ground observations. This approach can contribute to more accurate, faster and cheaper AGB estimates.

In this work we use geostatistical modeling to predict AGB in Montaña Palentina in Spain, which belongs to the Atlantic Forest. The rationale behind this is based on the fact that the response variable (biomass) is a spatial phenomenon that is present in a continuous domain and that is observed in a finite number of fixed or randomly chosen points. Inference for these models can be done using Bayesian and Frequentist approaches, [2]. However, the flexibility of the first face to the second, led us to choose it for analysis. In this way, we will use field data from the Fourth National Forest Inventory of Spain as well as remote data, provided by GEOSAT-2 satellite. Measurements such as texture, vegetation indices, as well as spectral variables are remote sensing data that are extracted from the reflectance bands from satellite measurements. In addition, we will also use data relating to the ground, such as land slope, altitude, among others.

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A new algorithm for inference in Hidden Markov models with lower span complexity

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Abstract

The maximum likelihood problem for Hidden Markov Models is usually numerically solved by the Baum-Welch algorithm, which uses the Expectation-Maximization algorithm to find the estimates of the parameters. This algorithm has a recursion depth equal to the data sample size and cannot be computed in parallel, which limits the use of modern GPUs to speed up computation time. A new algorithm is proposed that provides the same estimates as the Baum-Welch algorithm, requiring about the same number of iterations, but is designed in such a way that it can be parallelized. As a consequence, it leads to a significant reduction in the computation time. We illustrate this by means of numerical examples, where we consider simulated data as well as real datasets.

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Unravelling the mathematical tapestry – charting the statistical terrain: Navigating complexity in social science statistical studies, exploring the intricacies of social science research through mathematical lens

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Abstract

The complexity of statistical studies in social sciences stands as a central theme in this scientific communication, aiming to explore the intersection between mathematical methods and social phenomena. In a landscape where data stemming from diverse sources and contexts are frequently scrutinised, significant challenges arise, calling for advanced statistical approaches and a profound understanding of the nuances underlying the data. The multidimensional and heterogeneous nature of data in social sciences poses unique obstacles, necessitating statistical methods capable of effectively capturing this complexity. Techniques such as exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis emerge as valuable tools to identify latent patterns, underlying structures, and non-trivial relationships between variables, facilitating a deeper understanding of the social processes at play. However, the application of these methods is not devoid of challenges. The integration of statistical models with social theories demands a careful approach to ensure the validity and interpretability of results. Issues pertaining to sample representativeness, selection bias, and measurement instrument reliability need to be meticulously addressed to ensure the robustness of conclusions. Throughout this scientific communication, concrete examples of the application of statistical techniques in social science studies will be presented, highlighting not only the challenges faced but also the creative and innovative solutions proposed. By understanding and tackling the complexity of statistical studies in social sciences, we can advance the construction of more precise and informative models, thereby contributing to a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of contemporary social issues.

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Financial literacy as part of statistical literacy

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Abstract

The data from Eurobarometer in 2022 financial literacy in European union, best respondents score only 26% in UE27 countries and in Portugal just 16%. This justifies new leaning scientific standards [1]. Financial literacy depends on emotional literacy, mathematical literacy, statistical literacy in the communication, design, implementation, control and adjustment of the financial measures for successful financial planning at a given context [2].

1 Purpose: Know how to improve generational the financial literacy competencies of population. This research aims to prove with statistical and mathematical science how to foster the competences acquisition and retention in financial literacy [3].

2 Method: Using clustering for initial diagnose of intervention groups to early behavior detection. Fast Fourier transform analysis applied to several detectors and regression models to predict behaviors and suggest leaning courses [4], data cluster and posterior learning content to the identified levels of financial literacy knowledge [3].

3 Intended Results: Create green, buffer, and red zones for desired, tolerated and undesired behavior, respectively. Contribution for Standard adoption of financial literacy scientific curricular contents program for teachers according with the results from data.

4 Intended Conclusions: Financial literacy standard methodology will enrich individuals with best practices to promote desired financial behavior reducing the gap between what they desire to do and what they are skilled to do.

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Session V

Friday, 12th April, 16:35-18:05, VA1

Control problems with DDN-NS equations

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Abstract

In this work we present our recent results regarding a non-smooth distributed optimal control problem, related to the Navier-Stokes equations with mixed boundary conditions of a Directional-Do-Nothing type [1; 2; 3]. We also focus on giving a discretization [4], which allows to use a Newton-semismooth method, to obtain numerical solutions in a much faster way than the typical Picard method. Lastly, we also show some numerical results concerning the optimal control of a regularized version of the DDN-NS equations, with a velocity tracking cost functional [3; 5].

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An iterated local search algorithm for the traveling purchaser problem

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Abstract

The Traveling Purchaser Problem (TPP) is a generalization of the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) in which a list of items must be acquired by visiting a subset of markets [1]. The objective is to minimize the total cost sustained along the route, including purchasing and traveling costs. Due to the NP-hard nature of the problem [2], solving the TPP in an exact manner is computationally challenging, implying the need for heuristic approaches in order to obtain quality solutions efficiently. This study proposes an algorithm based on the metaheuristic Iterated Local Search (ILS), complemented by a route configuration procedure that adjusts the subset of markets in the solution. The algorithm is tested in benchmark instances, providing a performance comparison with other methods used in the literature [3; 4].

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Optimal control of a class of stochastic 3rd grade fluids equations

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Abstract

In a bounded and simply connected domain $\mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, $d = 2, 3$, with regular boundary $\partial\mathcal{D}$, we aim to control the dynamics of a class of stochastic incompressible third grade fluids. The control is introduced through a predictable stochastic force. The objective is to minimize a tracking-type cost functional, for which the velocity vector field is oriented towards a desired velocity profile, often referred to as the target. We recall the well-posedness results of the state equation, then prove some related stability results. Next, we study the well-posedness of the linearized state's solution and show that it coincides with the Gâteaux derivative of the control-to-state mapping. Furthermore, we study existence and uniqueness results for the corresponding backward stochastic adjoint system and finally derive the duality relation and necessary optimality condition for the control problem.

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Time-dependent strategy for enhanced blood flow modeling with boundary control

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Abstract

Understanding time-dependent blood flow dynamics in arteries is crucial for diagnosing and treating cardiovascular diseases. However, accurately predicting time-varying flow patterns requires integrating observational data with computational models in a dynamic environment. Due to the coarse resolution and limited accuracy of noninvasive measurement techniques such as ultrasound or phase-contrast magnetic resonance imaging (PC-MRI), discrepancies often arise between computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations and PC-MRI measurements [1; 2]. Assessing the origin of these discrepancies—whether from modelling errors, spatio-temporal averaging, or measurement errors—is challenging due to methodological limitations in data incorporation and control parameter handling within simulation frameworks. This study investigates the use of data assimilation and boundary optimization techniques to enhance the accuracy of time-dependent blood flow simulations. Our integrated approach combines tailored data assimilation methods with boundary optimization strategies to minimize the disparity between model predictions and observed data over time, thereby improving the fidelity of time-dependent blood flow simulations. Validation using synthetic time-series observational data with added noise demonstrates the effectiveness of our approach in achieving improved accuracy, providing valuable insights for cardiovascular research and medical practice.

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The MFS-SVD method for the Laplace equation in three dimensions

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Abstract

The method of fundamental solutions (MFS) has been widely used to solve boundary value problems (BVP) involving linear partial differential equations [2]. The classical MFS approach to approximate the solution of a BVP is to use a linear combination of fundamental solutions. The linear combination coefficients are chosen in such a way that the approximation satisfies the boundary conditions.

To determine coefficients, we need to solve the linear system $Ax = b$ for x , where A is a matrix and b is a vector containing the values associated with the boundary conditions. The main limitation of MFS is that the ill-conditioning of the matrix A can reduce the accuracy of the method [3].

We present three methods to reduce the ill-conditioning of the classical MFS for the Laplace equation in bounded star-shaped domains in 3D. The first method, which we call QR-MFS, involves using a reduced QR factorization of the matrix A . The idea of the other two methods, which we call SVD-MFS and Hybrid-MFS, is based in the expansion of the MFS basis functions in terms of spherical harmonics. By doing so, we obtain $A = (MF)^T$, where M only depends on the source points and F only depends on the collocation points. For SVD-MFS, we use a singular value decomposition (SVD) of M , while for Hybrid-MFS we consider the reduced QR factorization of F and then SVD in the matrix resulting from the multiplication of M with R . This leads to a better set of basis functions that spans the same approximation space as the classical MFS. Numerical results show that these approaches significantly reduce the ill-conditioning, resulting in higher accuracy compared to the classical MFS.

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Improving the conditioning of the method of fundamental solutions for the Helmholtz equation on domains in polar or elliptic coordinates

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Abstract

A new approach to overcome the ill-conditioning of the Method of Fundamental Solutions (MFS) combining Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) and an adequate change of basis was introduced in [1] as MFS-SVD. The original formulation considers polar coordinates and harmonic polynomials as basis functions and is restricted to the Laplace equation in 2D. In this work, we start by adapting the approach for the Helmholtz equation in 2D [4], and later extending it to elliptic coordinates. As in the Laplace case the polar coordinate approach has very good numerical results both in terms of conditioning and accuracy for domains close to a disk but does not perform so well for others domains, like an eccentric ellipse for example. In this sense, we consider the MFS-SVD approach in elliptic coordinates with Mathieu functions [3; 2] as basis functions for this last case. We illustrate the feasibility of the approach by numerical examples in both cases.

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Session VI

Friday, 12th April, 16:35-18:05, VA2

Fantastic normed spaces and where to find them

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Abstract

This talk is aimed to briefly expose our main research lines and the novelties obtained during these past years in collaboration with many colleagues (see for example [2] or [3]). With this goal in mind, we shall introduce the origin of the well-known *Tingley's problem* ([1]) as well as the normed space structures we work with and how they are *fantastically* linked between them.

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A Brown–Halmos theorem for generalised Toeplitz operators

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Abstract

The well-known Brown-Halmos theorem tells us when the product of two Toeplitz operators is the Toeplitz operator whose symbol is obtained by multiplying the symbols of each factor. We ask the same question about the product of generalised Toeplitz operators, i.e., compressions of multiplications to arbitrary closed subspaces of $L^2(\mathbb{T})$. In the end, we will see some applications of Brown-Halmos theorem for generalised Toeplitz operators.

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Discrete Wiener–Hopf operators on Orlicz sequence spaces

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Abstract

One of the main questions one can ask about a bounded linear operator on a Banach space is whether the operator is invertible. Sometimes this question can be very difficult to answer. A weaker form of this question is whether the operator is invertible modulo the ideal of all compact operators. Operators with this property are called Fredholm operators.

The aim of this work is to develop the Fredholm theory of discrete Wiener-Hopf operators with symbols which are periodic distributions. We concentrate on discrete Wiener-hopf operators acting on the Orlicz sequence spaces [1], which are far reaching generalizations of the Lebesgue sequence spaces. We try to extend the results for classical ℓ^p spaces [2] to the setting of Orlicz sequence spaces.

We extend the classical Brown-Halmos, Hartman-Wintner and Coburn theorems for discrete Wiener-Hopf operators to the setting of Orlicz spaces. Further, we give necessary and sufficient conditions for their Fredholmness if the symbols are continuous multipliers or, more generally, belong to the Douglas-type algebra $C_{\Phi} + \overline{H_{\Phi}^{\infty}}$.

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Fredholm criteria for the algebra generated by Wiener–Hopf operators with continuous symbols on Orlicz spaces

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Abstract

We extend the Fredholm criteria for Wiener-Hopf operators with continuous symbols on the Lebesgue space $L^p(\mathbb{R}_+)$, $p \in (1, \infty)$, obtained by Roland Duduchava in the late 1970s, to the setting of reflexive Orlicz spaces $L^\Phi(\mathbb{R}_+)$. We later combine this result with some techniques from the theory of commutative Banach algebras to derive a general Fredholm criteria for any operator T lying in the closed subalgebra generated by all Wiener-Hopf operators with continuous symbols.

Self-improving boundedness of the Hardy–Littlewood maximal operator over spaces of homogeneous type

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Abstract

A space of homogeneous type (Ω, d, μ) is a quasi-metric space (Ω, d) with a doubling Borel measure μ —and as a far-reaching generalization of the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^n with the Lebesgue measure, it constitutes a rich in tools setting for analysis. One may find an analogue of the Euclidean dyadic cubes there [1]; consider the Hardy-Littlewood operator

$$Mf(x) := \sup_{B \ni x} \frac{1}{\mu(B)} \int_B |f(y)| d\mu(y), \quad x \in \Omega,$$

perfectly defined due to the notion of a quasi-distance d and the associated balls B ; study the boundedness of M on various function spaces over spaces of homogeneous type, using the dyadic technique.

In this work, for quasi-Banach function lattices $X(\Omega, d, \mu)$ with the Fatou property, we generalize the result of Lerner and Ombrosi [2] about self-improvement properties of the maximal operator on quasi-Banach function spaces over \mathbb{R}^n . Namely, addressing multiple convexifications of the lattice $X(\Omega, d, \mu)$ defined as

$$X^{(r)}(\Omega, d, \mu) := \{\text{measurable } f : |f|^r \in X(\Omega, d, \mu)\}, \quad r > 0,$$

we prove that the following are equivalent:

- (i) M is bounded on $X(\Omega, d, \mu)$.
- (ii) For all $s > 1$, M is bounded on $X^{(s)}(\Omega, d, \mu)$ and

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 1^+} (s-1) \|M\|_{X^{(s)} \rightarrow X^{(s)}} = 0.$$

- (iii) There exists $r_0 \in (0, 1)$ such that if $r \in (r_0, 1)$, then M is bounded on $X^{(r)}(\Omega, d, \mu)$.

An important theoretic application of this result is the special case when $X(\Omega, d, \mu)$ is the variable Lebesgue space $L^{p(\cdot)}(\Omega, d, \mu)$.

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Polynomial collocation method for a class of singular fractional differential equations

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Abstract

In the present work we developed a polynomial collocation method for the class of singular fractional differential equations for $\alpha, \alpha_k \in \mathbb{R}$

$$(D_0^\alpha M^\alpha u)(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\ell} b_k(t) (D_0^{\alpha_k} M^{\alpha_k} u)(t) + f(t), \quad 0 < t \leq T, \quad (1)$$

where $q < \alpha \leq q + 1$, $\alpha > \alpha_k \geq 0$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, \ell$, $q \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $f, b_k \in C^q[0, T]$. The operator M^ν is the multiplication operator defined by

$$(M^\nu u)(t) = t^\nu u(t), \quad t \in (0, T], \nu \in \mathbb{R}, \quad u \in C([0, T]), \quad (2)$$

and D_0^α is the fractional differential operator of order $\alpha \in [0, \infty)$ ([3]) defined as the inverse of the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator J^α for $v \in J^\alpha C([0, T])$, i.e.,

$$(D_0^\alpha v)(t) = ((J^\alpha)^{-1} v)(t), \quad \text{and} \quad (J^\alpha u)(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} u(s) ds, \quad (3)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Euler Gamma function. By employing a suitable change of variables, we can demonstrate that the singular equation (1) is equivalent to a cordial Volterra integral equation. Using the theory developed by G. Vainikko (e.g. [1; 2; 3]), in [4] existence and uniqueness results for the solution of (1) were proved. In [5] we propose a polynomial collocation method to approximate the solution of (1), prove the convergence of the proposed method (on several spaces: $C^m[0, T]$ and $\mathcal{H}^{m,\beta}[0, T]$, $m \geq 0$). Additionally, we provide several numerical examples to illustrate the effectiveness of the numerical method.

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Session VII

Saturday, 13th April, 10:05-11:35, VA1

The marginalized LASSO estimator in difference-based partially linear models

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Abstract

The difference-based partially linear model [1] serves as an appropriate regression framework when both linear and nonlinear predictors are included in the dataset. However, when attempting to optimize the weights using this method, variable selection becomes challenging, particularly due to the presence of low-variance predictors. To address this issue, our study aims to introduce a novel methodology based on marginal theory, specifically tackled to handle such mixed relationships while placing emphasis on variable selection. Our proposal involves employing a marginalized LASSO estimator [2] with a penalty term that is less severe and correlated with the difference order. To assess the efficacy of our approach, we conduct extensive simulation experiments to numerically illustrate its effectiveness in both estimation and prediction when compared to the standard LASSO method [3], particularly in scenarios with low-dimensional setups. Furthermore, we use bootstrapping techniques to evaluate the performance of our proposed prediction method using the King House dataset.

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Machine learning algorithms to predict the solar and wind energies supply profiles

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Abstract

The focus of the current study is the efficient management of the levels of energy consumption, supply, and storage of a data center, aiming at minimizing the costs for clients while meeting sustainable goals [1]. One of the main challenges to achieve this goal, is the uncertainty associated to the production of renewable energies, more specifically, solar and wind energies. To overtake this challenge, different approaches have been proposed [6]. We will focus on the use of machine learning algorithms to predict the production of solar and wind power [2; 3].

The main goal of this work is to provide an initial prediction framework of the renewable energies supply profiles in a green data center, based on weather data [4; 5]. To do so, we will start by considering only two sources of renewable energy: solar and wind power. An analysis of the solar and wind time series will be provided. Different machine learning algorithms will be applied and compared to the state-of-the-art approaches. We will present some results and future work, including the following development of this work.

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A classification method based on a cloud of spheres

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Abstract

In [1], we propose a binary classification model to distinguish a specific class that corresponds to a characteristic that we intend to identify (e.g. fraud, spam, disease). The classification model is based on a cloud of spheres that circumscribes the points of such target class. It is intended to build a model based on a cloud and not on a disjoint set of clouds, establishing this condition on the connectivity of a graph induced by the spheres. To solve the problem, designed by a Cloud of Connected Spheres, a quadratic model with continuous and binary variables (MINLP) is proposed with the minimization of the number of spheres. The issue of connectivity implies in many models the imposition of an exponential number of constraints. However, because of the specific conditions of the problem under study, connectivity is enforced with linear constraints that scale quadratically with K , which serves as an upper bound on the number of spheres. This classification model is effective when the structure of the class to be identified is highly non-linear and non-convex, also adapting to the case of linear separation. Unlike neural networks, the classification model is transparent, with the structure perfectly identified. No kernel functions are used and it is not necessary to use meta-parameters unless it is intended also to maximize the separation margin as it is done in SVM. Finding the global optima for large instances is quite challenging, and to address this, several heuristics are proposed.

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Visualizing interval Fisher’s Discriminant Analysis results

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Abstract

In Data Science, entities are usually described by vectors of single-valued measurements. Symbolic Data Analysis can model more complex data structures such as intervals and histograms that possess internal variability. In this work, we propose an extension of multi-class Fisher’s Discriminant Analysis [2] to the interval scenario based on Mallows’ distance [1] and Moore’s algebraic structure [3]. To visualize the classification results of this method, we adapt the graphical displays proposed in [4] and [5] to interval-valued data, adding interpretability to the information summarized by the confusion matrix. We exemplify their relevance and applicability using real-world data [6] from the telecommunications sector, collected to detect Internet redirection attacks.

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Deep Learning for parameter estimation in reaction-diffusion PDEs for battery modeling

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Abstract

One of the key development areas in battery research is finding ways to use metallic anodes, like Zn and Mg, but avoiding lithium, due to safety issues. Unfortunately, use of post-Li batteries is impaired by poorly understood shape changes, responsible for various failure modes.

Over the past decade, a mathematical approach based on RD-PDEs, has been developed in [1], able to capture the essential features of unstable material growth in electrochemical systems in terms of Turing pattern formation. Parameter identification in the above PDE is crucial but challenging due to a methodological gap between theory and experiments.

In this talk, based on [2], we propose to apply Deep-Learning as a new approach for parameter estimation, instead of the more traditional PDE constrained optimization, as for example in [3]. We use a Convolutional Neural Network devised for our goals, trained with the numerical solutions [2] of the PDE model.

We will show that the CNN performs three tasks:

- i. automatic partitioning of the parameter space associated to the PDE model;
- ii. morphological classification of simulated and experimental patterns;
- iii. identification of the model parameters for experimental electrode images.

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Least energy solutions for coupled Schrödinger equations with Neumann boundary conditions

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Abstract

The main aim of this talk is to discuss the existence of nontrivial (and non semi-trivial) least energy solutions for a Neumann elliptic system with a critical nonlinearity, characterized by a cooperative-competitive behavior. Specifically, the system is

$$(\mathcal{P}_\beta) \begin{cases} -\Delta u + \lambda_1 u = u^3 + \beta uv^2 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ -\Delta v + \lambda_2 v = v^3 + \beta u^2 v & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial \nu} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial \nu} = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases}$$

where $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^4$ is a C^2 bounded domain, and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 > 0$.

The parameter $\beta \in \mathbb{R}$ captures the essence of cooperation-competition, assuming positive or negative values respectively.

The approach is variational and the idea is to minimize the energy functional on a suitable manifold of the Nehari type.

To deal with the critical power, we estimate the energy level, using the solutions of $-\Delta w = w^3$ in \mathbb{R}^4 and the solution for the scalar equations $-\Delta u_i + \lambda_i u_i = u_i^3$ in Ω , to establish a compactness condition based on the classical Cherrier's inequality.

Additionally, I will discuss potential extensions of this system for a quasilinear elliptic operator of the type:

$$Q(u) := -\operatorname{div}(A(x, u)\nabla u) + \frac{1}{2}D_s A(x, u)\nabla u \cdot \nabla u.$$

In this case the energy functional is only continuous and we can use critical point theory for continuous functional based on the concept of *weak slope*.

Session VIII

Saturday, 13th April, 10:05-11:35, VA2

Free-falling motion of an elastic rigid rod towards a Schwarzschild black hole

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Abstract

It is well known that the trajectories of free-falling test particles in General Relativity are given by timelike geodesics. The motion of extended bodies, however, is far more complicated [1; 2; 3], and the geodesic approximation is only valid in the asymptotic limit when the size of the body is much smaller than the local radius of curvature [4; 5; 6]. In this work, we study the motion of an elastic rigid rod which is radially free-falling towards a Schwarzschild black hole. This is accomplished by reducing the corresponding free-boundary PDE problem to a sequence of ODEs, which we integrate numerically. Starting with a rod at rest, we show that it is possible to choose its initial compression profile so that its midpoint falls substantially faster, or slower, than a free-falling particle with the same initial condition. This seems to be a purely kinematic effect, since on average there is no net transfer of elastic to mechanical energy.

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Topics in Laplace transforms

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Abstract

The Laplace transform is one of the most ubiquitous integral transforms in mathematics, having applicability in a myriad of areas ranging from Analysis and Probability to Statistical Physics and Number Theory. We address the problem of knowing under which circumstances it can be assumed that an analytic function on a vertical strip has a Laplace representation and by employing methods of Function Theory and the Heat equation developed in [1] and [2] we study how the determining measure changes across adjacent strips of analyticity.

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Resurgence of multicritical strings

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Abstract

Quantum field theories and string theories are most often studied using perturbative series expansions in powers of a small coupling constant. Such expansions tend to be asymptotic with zero radius of convergence, and offer no direct insight in non-perturbative physics. In recent years, the mathematical framework of resurgent analysis has proven to be an effective way to make sense of these perturbative series, and obtain fully non-perturbative descriptions of physical observables for any complex value of the coupling [1]. Doing so involves the construction of Stokes data to connect local expansions to obtain a global description. In this talk, I will discuss recent work on the resurgent analysis of matrix integrals and their double-scaling limits to multicritical string theories. I will focus on a novel conjecture on Stokes data that generalizes work on the Painlevé I equation presented in [2], and our tests through resurgent large-order analysis and direct matrix evaluation of integrals. [3]

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Pinching topological recursion

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Abstract

In this talk, I will discuss an interesting connection between two distinct analytical approaches to solve matrix integrals. On one side of the connection lies the method of orthogonal polynomials and the differential equations it yields, whose solutions fully describe the matrix integral. On the other side of the connection lies the theory of topological recursion, together with the perturbative representation of the matrix integral it provides. We will show how these two seemingly distinct approaches are linked by a geometrical procedure, ultimately reduced to the degeneration of compact Riemann surfaces [1; 2]. This link displays an interesting interplay between perturbative and non perturbative corrections to matrix integral solutions, well understood and organised within the context of resurgence. Finally, as motivation, we provide some examples where we explicitly check the validity of this connection.

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A physical primality test

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Abstract

In 1801, the German mathematician Carl Friedrich Gauss published *Disquisitiones Arithmeticae* [3], one of the first books in the field of Number Theory. In section *Duae methodi, numeros compositos a primis dignoscendi, illorumque factores investigandi*, articles 329 – 334, Gauss created a primality test, where he applied some of the theory developed in the previous chapters, such as quadratic residues and binary quadratic forms.

In this talk, we present this test using a new and modernized approach, along with an example of its application by means of an original physical device based on suggestions by Gauss, as developed in [1].

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A numerical scheme for optimization of Dirac eigenvalues

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Abstract

In this presentation, we explore the optimal shapes for the eigenvalues of the Dirac operator under infinite-mass boundary conditions, a matrix-differential operator characterized by complex boundary conditions. Given the challenging nature of this problem, we utilize the Method of Fundamental Solutions, a meshless method to numerically solve partial differential equations, to study and introduce new conjectures supported by numerical evidence. Drawing comparisons with classical results such as the optimality of the disk and the circular drum, we investigate analogous scenarios within the framework of relativistic quantum mechanics. We analyze the three lowest positive eigenvalues and their ratios, focusing on the relativistic counterpart of the Faber-Krahn inequality for the first eigenvalue, which has been established in the classical setting. Additionally, we present a new sharp upper bound for rectangles and we conjecture its potential extension to the class of quadrilaterals.

References

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